

METHODOLOGY

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A protocol and analysis of year-long simulations of global storm-resolving models and beyond

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Abstract

We propose a protocol to evaluate and analyze year-long simulations of global storm-resolving models (GSRMs). The proposed protocol complements an earlier 40-day simulation protocol under the DYAMOND (DYnamics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains) project to allow the analysis of the seasonal cycle and associated climatic relevant phenomena. This intercomparison aims to reveal how GSRMs, which can simulate mesoscale convective systems (MCSs) in the global domain, reproduce atmospheric large-scale structures related to convection beyond month-long simulations. The intercomparison for one-year simulations is conducted by either atmosphere-only models or atmosphere–ocean coupled models with atmospheric horizontal mesh sizes less than 5 km. We recommend the continuous four seasons from March 2020 to February 2021 as a target period for the intercomparison but with options for many groups to join more flexibly. The output variables are collected at 0.25° resolution, and archives of a small set of native grid variables are encouraged to analyze tropical cyclones and MCSs. Through the proposed global storm-resolving simulation, we will evaluate the climatological distributions of the atmospheric large-scale circulations, such as the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), monsoon, midlatitude jets, their time evolution, and the upscale impacts on them. We present sample analyses from a one-year simulation using the 3.5 km mesh Nonhydrostatic Icosahedral Atmospheric Model (NICAM), revealing the realistic zonal contrast of tropical precipitation, no double ITCZ structure, the reasonable midlatitude jet position and intensity but a weak bias of storm track activities, and a warm bias over the Eurasia during boreal winter. We also clarify the cross-scale interaction, such as the effects of cold pools on mean precipitation over the Maritime Continent through the precipitation diurnal cycle and the effects of resolved gravity waves on midlatitude mean flows. The proposed one-year simulation protocol is referred to as the “Sendai Protocol.” This protocol is not unique or definite for evaluating GSRMs; we prospect a hierarchical set of experiments from short-term to multi-year simulations as GSRM intercomparisons.

Keywords Global storm-resolving model, DYAMOND, Intercomparison experiments, NICAM, ICON

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1 Introduction

The emergence of global storm-resolving models (GSRMs) or global kilometer (km)-scale models in the world has demonstrated a promising spread of the capability of these models (Satoh et al. 2019; Stevens et al. 2019). GSRMs are global atmospheric models with horizontal mesh sizes less than 5 km, mainly with the non-hydrostatic governing equation in the dynamical core. GSRMs are expected to avoid ambiguity due to convective parameterization, which is adopted in coarser-resolution ($O(10\text{--}100)$ km mesh) global circulation models (GCMs) practically used for weather forecasts and climate projections. Thus, GSRMs, in principle, exclude the use of convective parameterization.

The first intercomparison experiment of GSRMs was conducted under the protocol called DYAMOND (DYnamics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains; Stevens et al. 2019), and its second phase (DYAMOND-winter; <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/Winter/index.html>) is conducted. These simulations cover the 40 days chosen to test the simulated initial evolution of weather systems comparable to the real observations and its transition to climatology, unique to each model after the initial spin-up of about 1–2 weeks. These intercomparisons showed that all the models reproduced realistic distributions of clouds, e.g., in terms of both synoptic and mesoscale structures, which look like the geostationary satellite image (Stevens et al. 2019). Judt et al. (2021) also showed that GSRMs can produce tropical cyclones (TCs) with a more realistic intensity distribution than coarser-resolution GCMs, although there are still uncertainties among GSRMs. Based on these encouraging demonstrations, the next step in testing the capability of GSRMs for climate system research is the GSRM intercomparison for longer-period (e.g., year-long) simulations before jumping to multi-decadal simulations, which are required to understand the near-future climate projection under global warming. These simulations are designed to obtain a climatology for the model that is not constrained by initial conditions.

Behind the above motivation is the fact that recent trends of increasing computational resources enable us to extend the GSRM simulations over a year in many groups worldwide (Takasuka et al. 2023; Rackow et al. 2024; Taylor et al. 2023; Hohenegger et al. 2023). One of the approaches in the Deep Numerical Analysis (DNA) project in Japan (Miura et al. 2023) is to accomplish a decadal simulation of the present climate using updated NICAM at 3.5 km horizontal resolution (Takasuka et al. 2024). Also, the NextGEMS project (<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>) and Destination Earth (DestinE) and its Digital Twin on Climate Change Adaptation (Hoffmann

et al. 2023; <https://destination-earth.eu/>) in Europe aim at multi-decadal climate projections, in which ICON, IFS-FESOM, and IFS-NEMO are used. Even if one could not run GSRMs for longer simulations at the current computer resources, the one-year simulation would be a promising step toward a near-future capability of running multi-decadal simulations.

A clear difference between one-year and one-month simulations can be the extent of the impacts of the spin-up period. In most periods of one-year simulations, the information from atmospheric initial conditions is almost lost; that is, the performance of one-year simulations is determined by the sea/land surface boundary condition rather than the initial condition. Hence, year-long simulations can offer a different scope of analysis targets from 40-day simulations. While cloud microphysics properties, which are equilibrated in less than ten days (Matsui et al. 2015; Roh et al. 2021), have been a good target for one-month simulations, the large-scale circulation and its seasonal evolution are suitable targets for one-year simulations, considering that the timescale of the large-scale overturning circulations with the cloud–radiation interaction is about one month (e.g., Hoskins et al. 2020; Hoskins and Yang 2020). This aspect is exemplified by the large-scale pattern associated with the seasonal cycle of the land–sea contrast, known as the monsoon circulation, and the seasonal evolution of the tropical precipitation belt known as the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) (e.g., Segura et al. 2022). We further require multi-year and multi-decadal simulations to know the interannual variabilities of the large-scale circulations and weather phenomena, the climatological mean states (generally defined as the time average of 30 years), and the trend of anthropogenic warming detected over a century timescale. Nevertheless, one-year simulations can bridge the preexisting DYAMOND simulations and multi-decadal simulations required for climate projection studies (e.g., HighResMIP: Haarsma et al. 2016; NextGEMS, DestinE, EERIE [European Eddy-Rich ESMs; <https://eerie-project.eu/>], or HighResMIPv2 [https://highresmip.org/assets/images/documents/UKCMIP7_Sept2023_HighResMIP_MalcolmRoberts_poster.pdf]). Also, Takasuka et al. (2024) showed that even one-year simulations are enough to reveal the impacts of GSRM physics on the representation of the large-scale climatological characteristics.

One of the questions is whether GSRMs offer added value from coarse-resolution GCMs for timescales longer than a month. According to the Report on Digital Earths Lighthouse Activity km-scale modeling workshop (World Climate Research Programme 2022), while the better treatment of convection in km-scale models has been demonstrated, there remain many open

scientific questions as to how this capability can improve the model performance at synoptic- to large-scale up to the general circulation. Segura et al. (2022) suggested a hint in this direction by analyzing an atmosphere–ocean coupled GSRM. They found that the structure and location of the tropical rain belt are reproduced over land but with struggles on the ocean. In addition, the better representation of prominent disturbances in the tropics (e.g., tropical waves, Madden–Julian Oscillations [MJO; Madden and Julian 1971], and TCs) in a GSRM has been confirmed (Takasuka et al. 2023), whereas previous studies have not presented results on how these phenomena affect the circulations in the extratropics. The question is how and whether the processes improved by GSRMs can influence the large-scale circulation established in one-year simulations proposed in this paper. While this paper presents an example analysis, more insightful investigations can be considered by individual researchers using the data set obtained from the intercomparison experiments.

The present paper aims to initiate a one-year simulation intercomparison using atmosphere-only models as well as atmosphere–ocean coupled models at the km-scale resolution. With the development of global storm- and ocean-eddy-resolving coupled climate models, this new proposed intercomparison can address important questions about whether GSRMs offer new perspectives on the climate without the ambiguity related to cumulus parameterization used in conventional GCMs. First, an experimental protocol for the one-year simulations with GSRMs is proposed. Then, we present example analyses of a one-year simulation conducted by the 3.5 km mesh Nonhydrostatic Icosahedral Atmospheric Model (NICAM; Tomita and Satoh 2004; Satoh et al. 2008, 2014) as sample results of GSRMs. The one-year simulation protocol is not a unique proposal for the further extension of the intercomparison of GSRMs, so we also review a family of intercomparison experiments of GSRMs considering the spatiotemporal-scale hierarchy of the climate system.

2 Methods/experimental designs

2.1 Concept

This subsection describes the concept and background that led to the definition of the new protocol. Those interested only in the specific experimental protocols may skip this section and proceed to Sect. 2.2.

We propose the year 2020 for the intercomparison of the simulation in Sect. 2.2. Here, we discuss the choice of the year of the intercomparison because the choice of the targeted year and the length of the simulation period is most relevant. One of the reasons for the choice of the year 2020 is that it can be continued as a simulation

following the DYAMOND-winter simulation, which begins on January 20, 2020, and runs until March 1, 2020 (<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/Winter/index.html>).

Choice of other years is also possible, however. In anticipation of the model evaluation with the satellite observation, any years after 2011 are desirable because of the launching of the Global Precipitation Measurement Mission (GPM, Hou et al. 2014) in 2011, although the A-Train observation (Stephens et al. 2018) decreased during the latter years of this decade. Other than that, the choice of the year may depend on the El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO) conditions and intraseasonal oscillation activities that can affect the pattern of large-scale circulations. For example, the ENSO evolution shows that the La Niña condition develops toward the end of 2020 and continues until the beginning of the year 2023 (https://origin.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/products/analysis_monitoring/ensostuff/ONI_v5.php). In contrast, the boreal winters of 2014/15 and 2015/16 are characterized by strong El Niño, and that of 2018/19 is also characterized by weak El Niño. As for the intraseasonal oscillation activity, several prominent MJO events were observed in some periods, such as October–December 2018 (<http://www.bom.gov.au/climate/mjo/#tabs=Time-longitude>). Also, the interannual variability of tropical cyclone activities shows that 2018 and 2019 are the active years of tropical cyclogenesis over the western North Pacific and that other years are also characterized by active (2017 and 2020) and inactive (2013–2015) hurricanes in the Atlantic (https://psl.noaa.gov/gcos_wgsp/Timeseries/Hurricane/hurr.atl.ace.data). Hence, each year has its characteristics in various aspects, and the year 2020 can be categorized as a relatively moderate year for both ENSO and MJO activities, which is suitable for understanding basic states.

In addition to choosing a simulated year, we must consider how long a spin-up time is sufficient to analyze the full one-year period. For the 40-day DYAMOND-summer/winter simulations, the first ten days are regarded as a spin-up period, and the following 30 days are analyzed for the one-month climatology. This period can, however, still be viewed as the predictable range of the synoptic-scale weather forecast; large-scale circulations, associated weather patterns, and cloud distributions are comparable to observations. Apart from this timescale, a one-year simulation has another initial evolution that concerns an overturning timescale of the large-scale circulation, such as the Hadley circulation, of which the overturning takes about one month or longer (e.g., Hoskins et al. 2020; Hoskins and Yang 2020). During this period, large-scale circulations and water vapor fields evolve to almost equilibrate the vertical structure,

particularly in the subtropical dry subsidence region, so it seems appropriate to add more than one month as a spin-up period to one-year simulations. Thus, we suggest that the total integration time should be at least 13 months. For example, if one starts a simulation on January 20, 2020, as per the protocol of the DYAMOND-winter, the simulation until February 28, 2021, is recommended, and the targeted analysis period will be between March 2020 and February 2021. If one may calculate a simulation by rewinding the initial condition to August 1, 2019, as done by the SCREAM group (Sect. 2.4), the simulation will be conducted until August 31, 2020. In this case, the targeted analysis period covers the typical four seasons from September 2020 to August 2021.

Our primary proposal is the intercomparison of atmosphere-only GSRMs whose horizontal mesh size is less than 5 km. At least one experiment suffices to join the intercomparison, but experiments with a larger ensemble size and those with different resolutions (as long as the horizontal mesh size is less than 5 km) can join. Although the atmosphere–ocean coupled simulation is optional and can join as another separate line of the intercomparison, the model complexity that includes atmosphere-only and atmosphere–ocean coupled GSRMs and multiple-resolution ocean models in the coupled simulations allows the intercomparison. For example, the 3.5 km mesh NICAM can be coupled with either 0.1°- or 0.25°-grid ocean model, COCO (Hasumi 2015), called NICOCO (Miyakawa et al. 2017). To examine the resolution dependency and connect with perspectives from conventional GCMs, we are interested in comparing simulation results from coarse-resolution atmospheric models with those of GSRMs.

We expect several differences in the choice of the model initialization and output variables from the DYAMOND-summer/winter. First, the initial (atmospheric and land) conditions can be arbitrarily in this protocol because the

one-year simulation intercomparison will not emphasize the initial evolution of the simulated fields. Rather, it is worth investigating the similarities and differences between these experiments using different initial conditions. Ensemble simulations in any variable configurations are welcome if a model group desires. As for the output variables, the size of the one-year simulation data is a practical issue, unlike short-term intensive experiments. Considering that one of the main analysis targets here is the distributions and evolutions of large-scale dynamic and thermodynamic fields, we only mandatorily request coarse-grained output data comparable to the available reanalysis datasets, with a horizontal resolution of 0.25°. The higher-resolution native grid data can also be requested for specific purposes of intercomparison, such as analysis of TCs, but they are optional for modeling groups. The systematic comparison of the fine-scale mesh data is suitable for other sets of short-term experiments, which will be discussed in Sect. 4.

2.2 Experimental design

We specify the experimental design of the protocol for the one-year simulation by GSRMs. The basic protocol is summarized in Table 1. As in the previous DYAMOND-summer/winter simulations, the horizontal grid interval of the GSRM intercomparison simulations must be less than 5 km, whereas the vertical resolution can be arbitrarily chosen. Of these lists, we request no use of cumulus parameterization and gravity wave drag schemes in principle toward fair comparisons among GSRMs. Nevertheless, the use of cumulus parameterization can be relaxed if it is guaranteed that deep convection is almost explicitly resolved (i.e., smaller contribution from deep convective parameterization).

Table 1 Basic protocol of one-year-long intercomparison experiment of GSRMs. (*) Options are available; see Table 2

Analysis period	From March 1, 2020, to February 28, 2021 (*)
Initial date	January 20, 2020, following the DYAMOND-winter protocol (*)
Horizontal resolution	Less than 5 km
Vertical resolution	Not specified
Physics schemes	Not specified, but sub-grid convective parameterization and gravity wave drag scheme must be switched off, in principle
Model	Atmosphere-only model (*)
Ensemble size	At least one, or any number
Output variables	0.25° in the 6 h interval for 3D variables and 1-h interval for 2D variables; see Tables 3 and 4
Initialization of land and ocean	Arbitrarily up to each group

Among many candidates for the choice of the year of the intercomparison, as discussed in Sect. 2.1, we propose the analysis period of the simulation:

From March 1, 2020, to February 28, 2021

This experiment enables analysis of the full one-year simulation and the analysis of the four seasons: March–April–May (MAM), June–July–August (JJA), September–October–November (SON), and December–January–February (DJF).

As described in Sect. 2.1, the initial condition is not strictly specified if it covers the analysis period plus a one-month spin-up period. Instead of using January 20, 2020, as the initial date, one may start on January 1, 2020, and conduct 14 months of simulation. As another example, the Cess-type+4 K simulations performed by the SCREAM (E3SM) group (see Sect. 2.5) can join the present intercomparison by extending the simulation by six months (i.e., until February 2021). Note that these experiments are viewed as a subset of HighResMIPv2 (Roberts et al. 2024 in preparation), the longer-period intercomparison experiment covering the suggested analysis period and those with +4 K SST. Furthermore, the groups that can conduct multi-year simulations, including 2020, can also select the proposed analysis period within those simulations. In this case, the date of the initial condition can be much earlier than 2020.

In line with the above possible initialization diversity, it is also arbitrary which initial data is used. One may use the ERA5 reanalysis data to initialize atmospheric states, following the protocol of the DYAMOND-summer/winter experiments. In contrast, there is another case in which the initial condition for the target period would be different from reality if one uses a preexisting multi-year simulation in which the first year is not the target year 2020. All such cases are acceptable because one of the main interests here is to examine how GSRMs spontaneously reproduce large-scale atmospheric fields under certain boundary conditions.

Although we highly recommend the analysis period shown in Table 1 for a group that will newly start a year-long simulation or has already had simulation data covering that period, another one-year analysis period can be used to join the intercomparison. Behind this compromise is the fact that an additional new one-year simulation by a GSRM for this intercomparison is a burden in some groups because of a lack of access to sufficient computational resource. We expect that this treatment will not be significant when comparing the general behavior of the one-year seasonal march. Thus, we invite existing arbitrary one-year simulations to the present intercomparison to further compare with the simulation for the designated year 2020; a possible option is the analysis of

the other year from March of the year (which is referred to as 20xx) to February of the following year (20xx + 1). Note that Sect. 3 presents a sample analysis of the one-year simulation but in a different year, 2011, which is currently available simulation data from the 3.5 km mesh NICAM. In addition, the start of the simulation can be shifted to any season; for example, a continuous one-year for the simulation from September to August of the next year in the order of SON, DJF, MAM, and JJA can be a choice (e.g., for the Cess-type+4 K intercomparison led by the SCREAM and PCMDI group).

We refer to the analysis period from March 2020 to February 2021 as Option 1, while the other period of the year is Option 2. This experimental configuration is shown in Fig. 1.

Although the present protocol is for one-year integrations, some of the research groups that have participated in previous DYAMOND projects may be unable to perform one-year integrations due to a lack of computing resources. To keep the activities of the research groups who do not access to sufficient computational power, we propose an option for a one-season experiment as a subset of the one-year experiment. Even this configuration makes it possible to discuss one of the goals of the one-year intercomparison: the model's atmospheric general circulation climatology that is free from the constraints of the initial values (e.g., Kinter et al. 2013), whereas one could not possibly discuss the seasonal marches. In this case, it would be appropriate to use March–May 2020 (MAM) as the target of the analysis, starting from the DYAMOND-winter experiment. Such a seasonal experiment would be added as Option 3 as an entry card for climate simulations with GSRMs and is regarded as another set of intercomparison experiments (Sect. 4). Table 2 summarizes the options for the above experimental protocol.

In addition to the initialization of the atmosphere, initializations of the ocean and land are also a matter of km-scale year-long simulations. The initial condition for oceanic states depends on whether an atmosphere model is coupled to the ocean (i.e., atmosphere–ocean coupled simulation). For atmosphere-only simulations, we propose that the sea surface temperature (SST) and sea ice are initialized with the observed oceanic data. We suggest using ESA-CCI (the European Space Agency Climate Change Initiative) with a horizontal resolution of 1/20°. ESA-CCI is the product used in EERIE and is updated continuously every six months. We allow using other SST datasets, including the OSTIA (the Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Ice Analysis) product, which has the same resolutions as ESA-CCI (Good et al. 2020). The SST product used for the initialization is also required as an oceanic boundary condition in the

Fig. 1 Integration periods for one-year experiments (Options 1 and 2) and its subset of a one-season experiment (Option 3)

Table 2 Options for the one-year experiments and its subset of a one-season experiment

	Analysis period	Initial condition	Comment
Option 1 (suggested)	March 1, 2020–February 28, 2021 (MAM, JJA, SON, DJF)	January 20, 2020, or arbitrarily chosen before February 1, 2020	Continuation from the DYAMOND-winter experiment or any multi-year simulation starting before 2020
Option 2	March 1, 20xx–February 28, 20xx + 1 (MAM, JJA, SON, DJF), or any continuous 4 seasons	Arbitrary chosen more than 1-month before the analysis period	
Option 3	March 1, 2020–May 31, 2020 (MAM, 2020)	January 20, 2020	Continuation from the DYAMOND-winter experiment

atmosphere-only simulation. We recommend that SSTs used for the boundary conditions be updated daily.

In the case of atmosphere–ocean coupled simulations, they normally require the equilibration of the ocean circulation. Nevertheless, the full spin-up of the deep ocean is probably unnecessary for this intercomparison if the drift of the ocean surface condition is not severe. Hence, each coupled modeling group can choose any methodologies for initializing the oceanic states, although one horizontal resolution of an ocean model should be 0.1° or less. Similarly, what is used to initialize the land surface condition is also arbitrary; one may use the reanalysis product or the model equilibrium state obtained from long-term simulations at coarser resolutions. However, technical difficulties may arise from the inconsistency

in topography between different resolutions. As for the other details specifications of the experimental setup, we follow the previous DYAMOND experiments (Stevens et al. 2019). Flexibilities remain for each modeling group if details are not specified. These flexibilities are suitable for sensibility studies, and each modeling group could explore their dependency.

We suggest that for common analysis, the resolution of the output variables is 0.25°, which is not necessarily the same as the model resolution. We request only the coarse-resolution data as mandatory because it is particularly for the longer-term simulation proposed here. A list of output variables is shown in Tables 3 and 4. The interval of the output variables is 6 h for the three-dimensional (3D) variables (snapshot values) and 1 h

for the two-dimensional (2D) variables (averaged and snapshot values). Each group can define the vertical levels of the 3D variables. We suggest 37 levels in the pressure coordinate that are the same as those in the ERA5 reanalysis: [1000, 975, 950, 925, 900, 875, 850, 825, 800, 775, 750, 700, 650, 600, 550, 500, 450, 400, 350, 300, 250, 225, 200, 175, 150, 125, 100, 70, 50, 30, 20, 10, 7, 5, 3, 2, and 1 hPa]. A part of these vertical levels is used by the NICAM simulation shown in Sect. 3. For ICON, 25 levels are generally used: [1000, 975, 950, 900, 875, 850, 800, 750, 700, 600, 500, 400, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 30, 20, 10, 5, and 1 hPa]. For example, for a 3.5 km mesh NICAM, employing 2-byte compression in netCDF

Table 3 List of 3D output variables. All the variables are at the 0.25°-grid resolution. The interval of the output variables is 6 h for snapshot values

	Standard variable name	Units
1	Geopotential height	m
2	Zonal wind velocity	m s^{-1}
3	Meridional wind velocity	m s^{-1}
4	Vertical wind velocity	m s^{-1}
5	Temperature	K
6	Relative humidity (for liquid water)	[unitless]
7	Specific humidity	kg kg^{-1}
8	Specific cloud water mass	kg kg^{-1}
9	Specific rainwater mass	kg kg^{-1}
10	Specific graupel water mass	kg kg^{-1}
11	Specific snow water mass	kg kg^{-1}
12	Specific cloud ice mass	kg kg^{-1}

Table 4 List of 2D output variables. All the variables are at the 0.25°-grid resolution. LW and SW in the list denote longwave and shortwave, respectively. The interval of the output variables is 1 h for averaged and snapshot values

	Standard variable name	Units		Standard variable name	Units
1	Total column ice water	kg m^{-2}	16	Upward SW radiation at the surface (Clear sky)	W m^{-2}
2	Total column liquid water	kg m^{-2}	17	Downward SW radiation at the surface (All sky)	W m^{-2}
3	Surface latent heat flux	W m^{-2}	18	Downward SW radiation at the surface (Clear sky)	W m^{-2}
4	Surface sensible heat flux	W m^{-2}	19	Precipitation	$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
5	Upward LW radiation at the TOA (All sky)	W m^{-2}	20	Total column water vapor	kg m^{-2}
6	Upward LW radiation at the TOA (Clear sky)	W m^{-2}	21	Surface pressure	Pa
7	Downward LW radiation at the TOA	W m^{-2}	22	Sea level mean pressure	Pa
8	Upward LW radiation at the surface (All sky)	W m^{-2}	23	2 m specific humidity	kg kg^{-1}
9	Upward LW radiation at the surface (Clear sky)	W m^{-2}	24	2 m temperature	K
10	Downward LW radiation at the surface (All sky)	W m^{-2}	25	10 m zonal wind velocity	m s^{-1}
11	Downward LW radiation at the surface (Clear sky)	W m^{-2}	26	10 m meridional wind velocity	m s^{-1}
12	Upward SW radiation at the TOA (All sky)	W m^{-2}	27	Surface temperature	K
13	Upward SW radiation at the TOA (Clear sky)	W m^{-2}	28	Zonal momentum flux at the surface	N m^{-2}
14	Downward SW radiation at the TOA	W m^{-2}	29	Meridional momentum flux at the surface	N m^{-2}
15	Upward SW radiation at the surface (All sky)	W m^{-2}	30	Vertically projected cloud cover	[unitless]

format, with a horizontal mesh size of 0.25° and vertical levels of ERA5 for the 3D variables, the data size for all output variables shown in Tables 2 and 3 for a one-year simulation is approximately 4 TB.

Archiving native grids or high-resolution data close to the original native resolution is optional. Collecting these data on a single archive site would be difficult, so each modeling group will be asked to archive their data. However, collecting a small set of 2D variables will be possible. For example, for tracking TCs, archiving high-resolution data, including the 10-m wind velocity, sea surface pressure, and precipitation, is preferable (Table 5). Table 5 lists useful variables for detailed analysis of convection, clouds, and cold pools. The interval of these 2D variables is ideally 1 h, but it can be 3 h. For the specific purpose of tracking organized convective systems, one may demand a higher interval, such as 15 min. For archiving, both averaged and snapshot values are suggested.

2.3 Computational challenges

As a reference to computational challenges in one-year GSRM simulations, Table 6 summarizes the computational aspects of NICAM with a 3.5 km horizontal mesh and 78 vertical levels. This performance was obtained under a time step of 10 s in the horizontally explicit and vertically implicit scheme (Satoh 2002) and the physics configuration following the requirements shown in Table 1 (i.e., no use of any cumulus parameterizations and gravity wave drag schemes; the use of the NICAM single-moment microphysics scheme; Tomita 2008; Roh and Satoh 2014). Simulated Years Per Day (SYPD) depends on the available resources of the computer nodes. In fact, in

Table 5 List of 2D output variables at native grid resolution. The interval of the output variables is 1 h (or 3 h) for both averaged and snapshot values

	Standard variable name	Units	Purpose
1	Sea level mean pressure	Pa	Tropical cyclone tracking
2	10 m zonal wind velocity	m s^{-1}	Tropical cyclone tracking
3	10 m meridional wind velocity	m s^{-1}	Tropical cyclone tracking
4	Precipitation	$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	Convection
5	2-m specific humidity	kg kg^{-1}	Convection and cold pool
6	2-m temperature	K	Convection and cold pool
7	2.5 km vertical wind velocity	m s^{-1}	Convection
8	5.0 km vertical wind velocity	m s^{-1}	Convection
9	7.5 km vertical wind velocity	m s^{-1}	Convection
10	Total column water vapor	kg m^{-2}	Cloud
11	Total column liquid water	kg m^{-2}	Cloud
12	Total column ice water	kg m^{-2}	Cloud
13	Upward LW radiation at the TOA (All sky)	W m^{-2}	Cloud and convection
14	Upward SW radiation at the TOA (All sky)	W m^{-2}	Cloud and convection

Table 6 Computational aspects in NICAM used for the one-year 3.5 km simulation

Computational aspects	Descriptions
Used supercomputer and nodes	Fugaku/2,560 nodes (122,880 cores; about 1.6% of all nodes in Fugaku)
Numerical precision	Mixed precision (Nakano et al. 2018): Double precision for the radiation scheme and single precision for other simulations
Used memory size	About 10.5 GB (Maximum during a simulation)
Simulated Years Per Day (SYPD) achieved	About 0.05 SYPD
Information about timing	24% for dynamics; 60% for physics; 12% for communication; and 4% for I/O

the case of using more nodes of Fugaku, we will achieve more SYPD almost proportional to the number of nodes.

2.4 Timeline

The intercomparison of the one-year simulation of GSRMs is the first trial, and considering the researcher cannot easily repeat the simulation, we allow slight protocol modifications. This constraint motivates us to proceed with the simulation in two phases: The first (Phase I) is to intercompare various simulations in order to define a strict protocol for the second phase; and the second (Phase II) is to repeat the simulation with a well-defined integration period and improved model configurations, with an expectation that the one-year integration by GSRMs would be more feasible and could be a standard test case in the future. As for the model improvement, we can utilize perspectives from a companion intercomparison; we propose a short-term experiment for physics evaluations using various observations, including the EarthCARE satellite (Illingworth et al. 2015) and the field observations (e.g., ORCESTR). This activity enables us to evaluate GSRMs in a process-oriented manner and to

improve the physical process schemes. The details of the short-term intercomparison for the EarthCARE evaluation and improvement experiments will be investigated in a separate proposal (See Sect. 4 for more details). After such improvements, we recommend conducting a similar one-year simulation with a new version of GSRMs in each group. Phase II can tell us how physical processes affect large-scale circulations and climatology via comparisons of one-year simulations of the two versions of GSRMs.

A detailed timeline is as follows. The initial proposal of Phase I is set out by this article in 2024, and we suggest finishing the experiments by the end of 2024. The first analysis based on the intercomparison results will be summarized in 2025 through a planned activity of the WCRP global km-scale hackathon in 2025. Phase II will start after model evaluation by the short-term intercomparison experiments, which will be conducted in 2025–2026. We expect each modeling group to update the model and then conduct a one-year simulation with the new version of GSRMs, so we aim for Phase II to be conducted in 2027–2028.

The above timeline of the series of experiments is shown in Fig. 2. The modeling groups can arbitrarily join any phase of the timeline, and we do not require joining all sets of the intercomparison experiments.

2.5 Existing activities and implications

Prior to this proposal of one-year GSRM simulations, several research groups have conducted year-long or multi-year simulations. Against this background, each group chose their favorite year to be simulated. Under the NextGEMS project, ICON, IFS, and UM are run from January 20, 2020, as a continuation of the DYAMOND-winter experiment and have completed about 5-year simulations as the NextGEMS Cycle 3 in a global coupled configuration (https://nextgems-h2020.eu/cycle3_hack/).

The NICAM group started a simulation on January 1, 2011, and has completed about a 10-year simulation (Takasuka et al. in preparation). The GFDL group has conducted a 15-month simulation with an additional+4 K simulation (Chen et al. 2022; Bolot et al. 2023). In the UK and European countries, the project EERIE is currently running century-scale simulations, using IFS-NEMO, IFS-FESOM, ICON, and UM-NEMO, with 0.1° and covers GSRM simulation for some years (<https://eerie-project.eu/>). The SCREAM group of E3SM, Department of Energy (DOE), is conducting a year-long simulation of the current and global warming conditions with a simulation period from August 1, 2019, to August 31, 2020 (personal communication).

The research groups with much more computational resources also aim for longer multi-year simulations for decadal or multi-decadal years (e.g., DNA, NextGEMS). In this context, the GSRM performance should be evaluated and improved in terms of the representation of the climatology and interannual variabilities. At this moment, however, it is not generally feasible to repeat many experiments for multi-year simulations by GSRMs, which is the difficulty in developing GSRMs. In the future, nevertheless, there will be other targets of the decadal simulations for intercomparison: the reproducibility of the ENSO, the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO), and other interannual variabilities. For example, the NextGEMS project will tackle this aspect using multi-decadal GSRM simulations with ICON and IFS, the integration period of which is 2020–2050, including the near future. It also aims to examine the change in extreme events associated with future global warming or decadal oscillations such as the Pacific Decadal Oscillation (PDO).

3 Analysis

3.1 Sample analysis

This section presents sample analyses of the 14-month simulation by the 3.5 km mesh NICAM initialized on January 1, 2011. We provide several examples of the seasonal evolution and/or mean of large-scale dynamic and thermodynamic fields (e.g., precipitation, midlatitude dynamics, surface temperature) and the associated upscale effects (e.g., roles of the diurnal cycle and gravity waves)

Fig. 2 Timeline of the series of intercomparison experiments

over the year-long simulation. To clarify the impacts of km-scale resolutions, we also show results of the corresponding 14 km mesh simulation, as needed. The analysis of the intercomparison experiments depends on the interest of each researcher who will access the intercomparison data. A further possible analysis is argued in the next subsection.

3.1.1 Tropical precipitation patterns

In conventional GCMs, the precipitation distribution in the tropics is not well simulated (e.g., Oueslati and Bellon 2015), and the reproducibility of ITCZ, the South Pacific Convergence Zone (SPCZ) is a challenge to be tested in the simulations by GSRMs. As one of the analyses for it, Fig. 3 shows horizontal distributions of precipitation and its zonal mean values for the annual and the four seasons: MAM, JJA, SON, and DJF. The left and right columns are obtained from the Global Precipitation Climatology Project (GPCP) Monthly Product as an observed reference and from NICAM, respectively. Note that the precipitation distribution and intensity in observation vary among the datasets, and we do not know whether GPCP is closest to reality (Sun et al. 2018). Although the precipitation amount simulated in NICAM is generally overestimated compared to GPCP (see the zonal and global mean), the location of tropical precipitation bands, including ITCZ, is well reproduced. We have no severe double ITCZ bias, which is a significant improvement from the previous climate simulation with 14 km mesh NICAM (Kodama et al. 2021). Also, the NICAM simulation reproduces a realistic zonal contrast over the Indo-Pacific region, except for DJF, during which simulated precipitation over the south Indian Ocean is overestimated. These results are due to the elaborate NICAM improvement in its cloud microphysics and turbulent processes (Takasuka et al. 2024). Meanwhile, the contrast between ocean and land precipitation and the bias of precipitation over land are issues to be discussed in this intercomparison (Hohenegger and Stevens 2022).

Here, we highlight the seasonal migration of ITCZ and SPCZ over the western and central Pacific, considering that both are important features connected to the Hadley circulation. Figure 4 shows the time–latitude diagram of monthly mean precipitation averaged from 160 ° E to 140 ° W for the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) observation (Fig. 4a) and NICAM (Fig. 4b). Overall, NICAM reproduces the time evolution and structure of the ITCZ and SPCZ precipitation except for boreal spring. The transition of the active precipitation regions from the Northern Hemisphere to the Southern Hemisphere is well simulated from October to February. No double ITCZ structure is realized, consistent with the result in Fig. 3. Meanwhile, the NICAM precipitation is

exaggerated in the Southern and Northern Hemisphere during February and boreal summer, respectively. The latter is probably related to the overly active Asian summer monsoon. More detailed interpretation of the simulated ITCZ position and intensity can be achieved by the analysis of the interhemispheric energetic imbalance and transport (e.g., Adam et al. 2016; Bischoff and Schneider 2016; Hwang and Frierson 2013; Takasuka et al. 2024).

3.1.2 Precipitation activity over the Maritime Continent and related upscale effects

The precipitation activity over the Maritime Continent is another good target of the GSRM intercomparison because it is an essential driver of the Walker circulation and is affected by the cross-scale interaction under the complex land–sea contrast. As shown in Fig. 5a and b, displaying the first harmonic amplitudes of the precipitation diurnal cycle (PDC) and the mean precipitation for the Integrated Multi-satellite Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) product, the active PDC in coastal regions and land corresponds to the active annual mean precipitation there. This result suggests the upscale connection between the sub-daily scale variations and large-scale structure, which is worth being tested in km-scale simulations.

Figure 5c and d shows the bias of the PDC amplitudes and annual mean precipitation in NICAM, respectively. The simulated PDC amplitudes are generally underestimated in some coastal regions, although those over land have diverse biases depending on areas. Note that the positive biases of PDC amplitudes over land are realized near high mountains, where the reliability of IMERG is poor quantitatively. As expected, the PDC features are consistent with the distributions of the mean precipitation bias; the simulated mean precipitation amount is deficient in the areas where PDC is weaker and vice versa. Hence, at least in NICAM, even km-scale resolutions are not enough to capture the realistic PDC amplitudes near and over land, which can be a source of biases in the Walker circulation.

Nevertheless, the advantage of km-scale simulations on the representation of upscale impacts of PDC is robust. Figure 5e shows the difference in the PDC amplitudes between 14 and 3.5 km horizontal resolutions. The 3.5 km mesh NICAM can amplify PDC over the Maritime Continent, which mitigates the weak bias of PDC in the coastal regions successfully. A possible reason for this resolution dependency and the bias, even in the km-scale NICAM, is the difference in the cold pool intensity. Figure 5f compares the lagged composite evolution of 1-hourly surface air temperature associated with precipitation events between the 3.5 km and 14 km mesh NICAM and moored buoy

Fig. 3 (a, b) Annual and (c–j) seasonal mean precipitation obtained from the (left) GPCP product and (right) 3.5 km mesh NICAM simulation. (c, d) March–April–May, (e, f) June–July–August, (g, h) September–October–November, and (i, j) December–January–February. The simulation started on January 1, 2011. The first two months are discarded to calculate 3-month precipitation

Fig. 4 Time–latitude diagrams of the monthly mean precipitation averaged from 160 ° E to 140 ° W over the Pacific for the **a** TRMM-3B42 product and **b** 3.5 km mesh NICAM simulation

observation at the TAO stations. Precipitation events are detected at the time with 1-hourly precipitation of more than 2 mm hr^{-1} , and those for NICAM are further limited to the grid points with the horizontally local maxima of precipitation. Note that the used buoy data were obtained at 6 stations [(2°N/S; 5°N; 8°N/S, 165°E) and (0°N, 180°E)] where both high-frequency (every 10 min) precipitation and surface air temperature data are available. Although the temperature drop appears

to be similar for the two NICAM simulations, this does not mean the similar cold pool intensity in consideration of the difference in the precipitation amount [10.2 mm hr^{-1} (16.7 mm hr^{-1}) for the 3.5 km (14 km) mesh at the peak time of precipitation events]; that is, the cold pool intensity per unit precipitation is stronger for the 3.5 km mesh than the 14 km mesh. As for the observation, the temperature drop is larger even under weaker precipitation than in NICAM. Thus, cold pools

Fig. 5 **a, b** Horizontal maps of **a** the first harmonic amplitudes of the precipitation diurnal cycle (PDC) and **b** mean precipitation in the IMERG product from March 2011 to February 2012. **c, d** As in **(a, b)**, but for the difference in the **c** PDC amplitude and **d** mean precipitation for the 3.5 km mesh NICAM from those for IMERG. **e** Same as **c**, but for the difference between the 3.5 km mesh and 14 km mesh NICAM. **f** Time evolution of lagged composite surface air temperature anomalies during precipitation events for the 3.5 km (blue) and 14 km (orange) mesh NICAM and moored buoy observation (gray dashed). The reference time for composite ($t=0$ h) is when precipitation events are detected. Anomalies are from the ± 12 -h mean. Peak values of the composite precipitation amount during precipitation events are also denoted

in the observation and 3.5 and 14 km mesh NICAM are more significant in that order. This magnitude relationship is consistent with that of the PDC amplitudes in coastal regions, which supports the notion obtained by Yokoi and Kajikawa (2024).

To sum up, the representation of cold pools can affect the mean convection activity over the Maritime Continent through the simulated PDCs in coastal regions. It is worth intercomparing how this upscale

effect from mesoscale convection to the mean precipitation pattern is represented in GSRMs.

3.1.3 Midlatitude circulations: westerly jets and storm track activities

In addition to the analysis for the tropics, the evaluation of midlatitude circulations, which previous studies have devoted little attention to, is important in the context of GSRMs getting into the earth system modeling. Here,

we briefly overview the seasonal evolution of midlatitude westerly jets and the storm track activities (STAs) in boreal winter. It is worth examining STAs in realistic GSRM simulations because Schemm (2023) showed that long-standing biases of equatorward and weak STAs in conventional GCMs (e.g., Priestley et al. 2020) can be reduced by diabatic processes resolved at km-scale resolutions at least on an idealized aquaplanet.

Figure 6a and b compares the time–latitude diagrams of the zonal mean 300-hPa zonal winds between the Japanese 55-year Reanalysis (JRA-55) data (Kobayashi et al. 2015) and the NICAM simulation. In JRA-55 (Fig. 6a), we can confirm the enhanced midlatitude (30° – 60° N/S) westerly jets in the winter hemisphere and the meridional migration of the upper tropospheric westerlies, especially in the Southern Hemisphere. These observed seasonal changes in the westerly jet position and intensity are realistically simulated in NICAM (Fig. 6b). This is drastically improved from the 14 km mesh HighResMIP NICAM simulation (Kodama et al. 2021) because of both higher (km-scale) resolutions and the model improvements by Takasuka et al. (2024). Nevertheless, NICAM still struggles with simulating the more detailed behavior of the midlatitude jets; for example, the double jet structure at

300 hPa around 30° – 60° S in May–June is not so well represented.

As for STAs, Fig. 6c and d shows horizontal distributions of meridional eddy heat fluxes at 850 hPa in the Northern Hemisphere during DJF for JRA-55 and NICAM, respectively. Note that eddy components are defined as 8-day high-pass-filtered variations. As expected from the realistic representation of the westerly jet position (Fig. 6a and b), the meridional position of STAs in NICAM is almost consistent with that in JRA-55 over the Pacific and Atlantic, although it tends to be displaced equatorward slightly on the downstream side. In contrast to this good STA position, the STA amplitude in NICAM still has a weak bias over both basins, which is out of the expectation based on Schemm (2023). This difference seems not to be interpreted simply by the bias of the baroclinicity because the intensity of the westerly jets in NICAM is not underestimated during the boreal winter (Fig. 6b). The interpretation for this would be enriched by the intercomparison of various kinds of fields affecting the STAs (e.g., surface heat fluxes, orography), which have been rarely featured in GSRMs.

Fig. 6 (a, b) Time–latitude diagrams of zonal mean monthly mean zonal winds at 300 hPa ($m s^{-1}$) for the **a** JRA-55 reanalysis data and **b** 3.5 km mesh NICAM simulation. Contours in **b** represent the evolution in JRA-55. The contour interval is $8 m s^{-1}$, with zero contours omitted. **c, d** Horizontal distributions of boreal winter (DJF) mean meridional eddy heat fluxes ($m s^{-1} K$) for **c** JRA-55 and **d** NICAM. Eddy components are defined as anomalies filtered for periods less than 8 days. Contours in **d** represent the fluxes for JRA-55. The contour interval is $4 m s^{-1} K$, with zero contours omitted

3.1.4 Interaction between the midlatitude westerly jets and gravity waves

One of the possible upscale impacts in the midlatitude dynamics is the role of gravity waves (GWs) in the tropospheric and stratospheric westerly jets. For example, the subtropical jet is known as a source of nonstationary GWs (e.g., Plougonven et al. 2003; Kawatani et al. 2004), which can contribute to maintaining the midlatitude large-scale circulations. It is interesting to examine how well this aspect can be represented by GSRMs, which are expected to resolve GWs explicitly to some extent.

Figure 7a shows the meridional–vertical structure of zonal mean zonal winds in the Southern Hemisphere during JJA for the 3.5 km mesh NICAM, and Fig. 7a and b compares its bias between the 3.5 and 14 km mesh. In the 3.5 km mesh simulation, the subtropical jet core is located at 30° S, and the jet speed around it tends to be overestimated. Nevertheless, the zonal wind bias around the subtropical jet is much smaller than the 14 km mesh simulation, especially above 100 hPa in 30°–60° S (see contours in Fig. 7b). It is possible that this good point results from the more realistic interaction between mean flows and GWs excited near the subtropical jet spontaneously.

To test this speculation, we first examine net upward fluxes of the eastward momentum associated with GWs in the 3.5 km mesh NICAM (Fig. 7c) and their difference from the 14 km mesh (Fig. 7d). Note that GW components are defined as anomalies filtered for zonal wavelength shorter than 1000 km. In Fig. 7c, upward transport of westward momentum by GWs is prominent above the subtropical jet core and on its polar side, and this momentum transport is more active in the 3.5 km mesh NICAM than in the 14 km mesh (Fig. 7d). These results imply that the km-scale resolution models can certainly resolve more GWs and that resolved GWs in the midlatitude can decelerate the westerly jet in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere.

Based on this insight, we further compute the Eliassen–Palm (E–P) flux $F = (F_\phi, F_{z^*})$ to quantify the effects of GWs on zonal mean zonal winds:

$$F_\phi = \sigma \cos \phi \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial z^*} \frac{\overline{v'\theta'}}{\partial \theta / \partial z^*} - \overline{u'v'} \right),$$

$$F_{z^*} = \sigma \cos \phi \left(\left[f - \frac{1}{a \cos \phi} \frac{\partial \bar{u} \cos \phi}{\partial \phi} \right] \frac{\overline{v'\theta'}}{\partial \theta / \partial z^*} - \overline{u'w'} \right),$$

where u , v , and w are zonal, meridional, and log- p vertical wind velocity, respectively; θ is potential temperature; z^* is log- p height; σ is defined as $e^{-z^*/H}$ (H : scale height); f is the Coriolis parameter; a is Earth's radius; and overbars and primes denote the zonal mean and deviations from it, respectively. Figure 7e shows the meridional–vertical cross section of the E–P flux associated with GW components and its divergence, as well as zonal mean zonal winds, for the 3.5 km mesh NICAM. Also, Fig. 7f displays the difference in the E–P flux divergence between 3.5 and 14 km mesh. As expected, the E–P flux is directed upward and poleward away from the subtropical jet core, and its convergence is remarkable above 200 hPa in 45°–60° S (Fig. 7e). This flux convergence to the south of 45° S is stronger in the higher-resolution simulation (Fig. 7f), indicating the more deceleration of the upper tropospheric and lower tropospheric westerly jet by more resolved GWs. These results are consistent with the bias reduction of zonal mean zonal winds in the 3.5 km mesh NICAM (Fig. 7a and b), which confirms the upscale impacts of GWs on large-scale circulations as a merit of GSRMs.

3.1.5 Surface temperature

Figure 8 shows the time–latitude diagram of the monthly mean 2 m height temperature averaged at 30°–150° E for the JRA-55 reanalysis and NICAM simulation. This figure is intended to examine the surface temperature bias over the continent because the NICAM simulation is conducted under a specified SST condition with a slab ocean model. Note that the topography in NICAM is not the same as the observation, so the difference in the elevation is one reason for the bias. Figure 8 reveals that the boreal summer Eurasian continental temperature is well reproduced. In contrast, there is a warmer bias in the high latitude higher than 50°N in the boreal winter partly because of less cloud cover. Considering that the land–sea temperature contrast drives the monsoon systems, the realistic surface temperature of the Eurasian continent in the summer leads to a better simulation of the Southeast Asian precipitation associated with the Asian summer monsoon (Fig. 3e and f).

(See figure on next page.)

Fig. 7 (a, b) Latitude–height cross sections of the bias (from JRA-55) of zonal mean zonal winds during JJA (shading) for the a 3.5 km and b 14 km mesh NICAM. Contours in a and b indicate zonal mean zonal winds for the 3.5 km mesh and their difference from the 14 km mesh, respectively. Contour interval in b is 2.5 m s⁻¹, with negative (zero) contours dashed (omitted). c, d As in a, b, but for c zonal mean net upward fluxes of eastward momentum by GWs and d their difference from the 14 km mesh. e, f As in c, d, but for e the E–P flux associated with GW components (vectors) and its divergence ($\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}$; shading), and f the difference in $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}$ from the 14 km mesh

Fig. 7 (See legend on previous page.)

Fig. 8 Time–latitude diagrams of the monthly mean 2-m height temperature averaged from 30°E to 150°E for the **a** JRA-55 reanalysis data and **b** 3.5 km NICAM simulation. Contours in **b** are deviations from JRA-55. The contour interval is 1.5 K, with negative (zero) contours dashed (omitted)

Conventional GCMs still have difficulties in the realistic simulation of the land surface temperature, even when SST is specified for atmosphere-only models, which can affect the reproducibility of large-scale precipitation patterns (Zhou and Xie 2017). For atmosphere–ocean coupled models, the diagram, like Fig. 8, represents the SST bias if the longitudes are selected over the ocean (e.g., 140° W–160° E as in Fig. 4).

3.2 Perspectives on further analysis

It goes without saying that large-scale dynamic and thermodynamic patterns and upscale impacts on them other than those in the previous subsection (Figs. 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8) are also of great interest because the basic model performance should be evaluated comprehensively in anticipation of a forthcoming km-scale climate simulation. To satisfy this point, we welcome an analysis like Peixoto and Oort (1984) for various variables. It is

interesting to examine how different the reproducibility of hydrological fields related to clouds, precipitation, and moisture in GSRMs is among themselves and from that in conventional GCMs.

One of the specific interests in this context is the asymmetry in precipitation and net energy input between the Northern and Southern Hemispheres and associated cross-equatorial energy transportation (e.g., Kang et al. 2009; Hwang and Frierson 2013; Bischoff and Schneider 2016). Since the variability of the Hadley circulation is closely linked with the seasonal change of ITCZ, the above analysis helps interpret the intermodel spread of the evolution of large-scale precipitation patterns (cf. Figures 3 and 4), as described in Sect. 3.1.1. In fact, Takasuka et al. (2024) showed that the interhemispheric energetic view applies to understanding the single or double ITCZ structure in a GSRM-type simulation.

In addition to comparing the annual cycle, it is also important to address the detailed behavior of large-scale circulations in a specific season, as typified by the monsoon systems driven by the land–sea surface contrast. The boreal summer (June–July–August–September; JJAS) mean circulation characterizes the East Asian and Indian monsoon circulation, which greatly controls the hydrological cycle around populated areas in Asia, tropical cyclogenesis, and midlatitude extreme weather through teleconnections. Furthermore, in the boreal winter season (DJF), the Australian summer monsoon becomes prominent, and its activity may be closely tied to the MJO activity (e.g., Hendon and Liebmann 1990). Thus, toward a deeper understanding of the land–atmosphere coupling processes (e.g., Müller et al. 2021; Lee and Hohenegger 2024) as well as the interaction between moist convection and large-scale circulations, it is an interesting topic to evaluate how these monsoon onset and fluctuations are represented in GSRMs. This analysis can be aided by the examination of the seasonal-to-sub-seasonal variabilities of the following indicators of monsoon activities; the representative monsoon indices such as Indian Monsoon and Western North Pacific Monsoon Indices (Wang and Fan 1999; Wang et al. 2001), Webster and Yang Monsoon Index (Webster and Yang 1992), and Australian Monsoon Index (Kajikawa et al. 2010); the surface pressure over the North Pacific, or the intensity of the North Pacific High; and the land–sea contrast of precipitation (e.g., Hohenegger and Stevens 2022). In consideration of the diversity of land surface intermodal differences in the DYAMOND-winter (Miyakawa et al. in preparation), the comprehensive interpretation of monsoons simulated in GSRMs requires the intercomparisons of the land surface temperature, the surface

solar insolation affected by cloud cover and thickness, and the model topography.

As revealed in the DYAMOND-summer/winter activities, phenomena on intraseasonal and shorter time-scales are still perfect targets for GSRMs. Because the integration period is largely prolonged in comparison with the previous two DYAMOND simulations, we can discuss more statistical properties of TCs, including TC genesis and tracks and the wind–pressure relationship indicating TC dynamics, simulated in GSRMs, which can represent both large-scale circulations and the internal structure of TCs (Judt et al. 2021). The intra-seasonal variability (ISV) represented by the MJO and the Boreal Summer Intraseasonal Oscillation (BSISO; Kikuchi et al. 2021; or the boreal summer MJO) is also worth being discussed using GSRMs. Although we cannot fully describe the statistical features of the simulated ISVs because of a few events in one-year simulations, it is important to examine how the MJO is spontaneously reproduced in GSRMs away from initial value problems (e.g., Suematsu et al. 2022). The statistical analysis of mesoscale convective systems (MCSs) and their impacts on large-scale circulations by momentum transport using the year-long GSRM data is also within a scope (e.g., Feng et al. 2023; Ma et al. 2022; Miyakawa et al. 2012; Moncrieff et al. 2017).

An advantage of GSRMs is that high-resolution data provide information about extreme events. For instance, the extremes of temperature, precipitation, or winds are designated by the percentile within a coarse-resolution grid, such as 99 or 99.9 percentile within $2.5^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ grids. Nevertheless, we cannot analyze the details of extreme statistics only using stored coarse-resolution data in Tables 3 and 4, so we will consider an online analysis of the extremes with a smaller output data size or will use the data on native grids shown in Table 5. Still, the intercomparison of the extremes will be a target of Phase II.

An important motivation for one-year simulations is to examine the benefits, issues, and upscale effects in km-scale global models regarding the representation of large-scale circulations and their seasonal march. Also, the sensitivity of microscopic cloud microphysics and turbulent mixing processes on macroscopic fields should be examined, which has already been recognized by the NICAM team (Miura et al. 2007; Miura 2019; Takasuka et al. 2024). In this line, as described in Sect. 2.4, we propose the intercomparison of Phase II to compare the two types of simulation: a control simulation obtained by Phase I and an improved simulation from Phase II with the evaluation by intensive observations (see Sect. c).

4 Toward a unified hierarchical protocol for GSRM intercomparison

While the present article defines a protocol of one-year-long simulations for the GSRM intercomparison, it is not a unique extension of the previous DYAMOND projects; rather, it should be seen as part of a unified hierarchical protocol for assessing the systematics of GSRMs. Following this idea, we propose a set of GSRM hierarchical intercomparison experiments, which are summarized in Table 7. These intercomparison experiments build on and incorporate previous protocols and include sensitivity studies following standard practices and experiences from earlier intercomparisons. Also, this set for GSRM intercomparison is designed to be accessible to groups with differing amounts of computational resources and with models in differing stages of development, and it hopes to develop a family of models that can be used in initiatives such as Earth Virtualization Engines (EVE; Stevens et al. 2024). For example, considering that not all research groups will necessarily have access to the computational resources for one-year km-scale simulations, we incorporate a one-season experiment into the hierarchical intercomparison. This experiment is already introduced as a subset of the present protocol in Table 2 (see Sect. 2.2) but can be regarded as an independent intercomparison experiment. In fact, the boreal summer season experiment JJA can be used to study TC activity in the northern hemisphere (e.g., Kinter et al. 2013), suggesting that such a relatively shorter period experiment is useful to understand the model climatology.

While details of these GSRM intercomparison protocols will be discussed extensively in separate papers, here we specifically stress two threads of the experiments in this set, which have a mutually complementary relationship with the year-long intercomparison experiment for its interpretation and improvement; one is for the evaluation of GSRMs with the aid of relatively short (i.e., about one month) experiments under a realistic configuration with rich observational datasets obtained from an intensive field observation campaign and new satellite observations. The other is to understand the systematic behavior of GSRMs with the aid of idealized experiments.

The first thread aims to provide a detailed fine-scale analysis of GSRMs using intensive observational data from a week to a month. One example is the work by Roh et al. (2021), who analyzed the DYAMOND-summer data by applying the satellite simulator and compared the vertical profiles of clouds with those obtained by CloudSat and CALIPSO. However, Roh et al. (2021) could not systematically compare other model data because the 3D hydrometeor data of the other models were unavailable. Thus, the next intensive intercomparison will require various high-frequency and high-resolution output data to compare with the observation data. In this context, the EarthCARE satellite observation (Illingworth et al. 2015) and the ORCESTRA field measurements (<https://orcestra-campaign.org/intro.html>) are helpful for this plan. The EarthCARE satellite was launched May 2024, and the ORCESTRA campaign took place between Aug 10 and Sept 30 2024 with more than 20 coordinated EarthCARE

Table 7 A set of global storm-resolving model intercomparison experiments. The present study covers the experiments with (*). For the one-season experiment, see Table 2, Option 3

Basic atmosphere experiments	Summer (40 days; DYAMOND-summer) Winter (40 days; DYAMOND-winter) 1 season (3 months) (*) 1 year for annual cycle (*) 30 years or AMIP Scenario run Short-term experiment for evaluation with intensive observation Ensemble of extreme case studies (control and pseudo-global warming condition)
Coupled prediction systems	Summer (40 days; DYAMOND-summer) Winter (40 days; DYAMOND-winter) 1 season (3 months) (*) 1 year for annual cycle (*) 30 years
Conceptual studies	1 year for the annual cycle with +4 K 30 years for AMIP +4 K Aqua planet experiment (e.g., Qobs and +4 K) Patterned experiment for future TC changes

under flights across the Atlantic ITCZ. August 10–September 30.

In idealized experiments, an aqua planet experiment (APE) is a candidate for intercomparison, as Blackburn and Hoskins (2013) describe its aims and importance. The experiments will follow what Neale and Hoskins (2000) proposed with “Qobs” SST, but the protocol of APEs is not strictly specified here. In fact, the APE intercomparison of GSRMs has already been planned as a counterpart to the realistic year-long experiment we propose in the present paper (Suematsu et al. 2023). In addition, for a study of cloud response and the climate sensitivity of GSRMs, an additional +4 K warming experiment for APE is also possible, which was proposed for CMIP5 (Taylor et al. 2012). The importance of using APE in understanding cloud response to warming is stressed by Stevens and Bony (2013).

In addition to the above two branches, response to warming can be tested in a realistic simulation as conceptual studies. The Cess-Potter-type +4 K simulation (Cess et al. 1990) is suggested and proposed by the SCREAM (E3SM) and PCMDI group for a pair of 13-month simulations using the same present-day year-long simulation proposed in the present paper as the baseline simulation. A Cess-Potter intercomparison would allow us to assess the spread of climate feedback and climate sensitivity among GSRMs and determine whether structural differences exist compared to GCMs that heavily rely on cumulus parameterizations. Because of the uncertainty of the future projection of SST change (Sobel et al. 2023), experiments with specified SST patterns are also suggested, particularly in TC change studies (Zhao and Knutson 2024).

Numerical simulations for shorter weather scales (one or two weeks) remain important for some research groups. In fact, there is a demand for more organized intercomparison experiments on extreme weather events such as TCs and heavy rainfall events. It can be proposed to list examples of recent extreme weather events and to characterize the model as an ensemble of many case experiments. Pseudo-global warming experiments for each extreme case can also be proposed to estimate the anthropogenic influence (e.g., Reed et al. 2020, 2022; Tanaka et al. 2023).

5 Summary and conclusions

Global storm-resolving models (GSRMs) that resolve atmospheric circulations with a km-scale have become one of the core branches of weather and climate modeling studies. The existing computer resources, however, are limited, and it is still not feasible for GSRMs to conduct centenarian climate simulations, as proposed by the CMIP6 protocol. While the previous

GSRM intercomparison experiments were for 40 days of DYAMOND-summer/winter experiments (Stevens et al. 2019; <https://www.esiwace.eu/the-project/past-phases/dyiamond-initiative/services-dyiamond-winter>), we consider a methodology to evaluate and compare GSRMs in climate-scale simulations as a next step. Toward this end, we propose a one-year simulation protocol for one of the forthcoming intercomparisons of GSRMs. We target a specific year of the one-year simulation and mainly examine the annual cycle of the large-scale circulation. In particular, precipitation and its effect on large-scale circulation are a main focus of the simulations because it is interesting to examine how fine-scale resolved convection can be connected to large-scale circulations and how it differs from that in coarse conventional GCMs with convective parameterization. The proposed one-year simulation protocol is referred to as the “Sendai Protocol.”

As an example of the simulation, we conducted a 3.5 km mesh simulation using the Nonhydrostatic Icosahedral Atmospheric Model (NICAM) starting on January 1, 2011. We then evaluated it from the following large-scale aspects: the annual and seasonal (4 seasons) precipitation distributions (Fig. 3); the latitudinal variations of monthly mean precipitation over the central Pacific (Fig. 4); the zonal mean zonal winds at 300 hPa (Fig. 6a and b), and the near-surface temperature mainly over Eurasia (Fig. 8); and the storm track activities at 850 hPa during the boreal winter (Fig. 6c and d). We also clarified several upscale impacts on large-scale circulations, such as the relationship between the cold pools, precipitation diurnal cycle and mean precipitation over the Maritime Continent (Fig. 5), and the effects of vertical momentum transport by gravity waves on the midlatitude circulations (Fig. 7). Although they are intended to show only a part of the simulation performance, these help us grasp the basic characteristics of the model simulation.

The intercomparison of one-year simulations with GSRMs can be put on a unified hierarchical protocol used to assess the systematics of GSRMs. In this hierarchy, we will cover various kinds of temporal ranges for both atmosphere-only and ocean coupled simulations, from sub-seasonal scales (40 days) to decadal scales and historical runs. Of these preexisting and planned protocols, the one-year GSRM simulation protocol gives us the first opportunity to compare the basic large-scale characteristics among participating GSRMs and to analyze the model results from each of our perspectives. We expect such analyses to advance our understanding of the processes behind atmospheric circulations, improve the models, and bridge GSRMs to simulate longer climate simulations, as suggested by Stevens et al. (2024).

Abbreviations

AMIP	Atmospheric Model Intercomparison Project
APE	Aqua Planet Experiment
BSISO	Boreal Summer Intraseasonal Oscillation
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
DJF	December-January-February
DNA	Deep Numerical Analysis
DOE	Department of Energy
DYAMOND	DYnamics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains
E3SM	Energy Exascale Earth System Model
EERIE	European Eddy-Rich ESMS
ENSO	El Niño–Southern Oscillation
E–P flux	Eliassen–Palm flux
ESA-CCI	The European Space Agency Climate Change Initiative
EVE	Earth Virtualization Engines
GCM	General Circulation Model, or Global Climate Model
GFDL	Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory
GPM	Global Precipitation Measurement Mission
GSRM	Global Storm-Resolving Model
GW	Gravity Waves
ICON	Icosahedral Nonhydrostatic Weather and Climate Model
IMERG	Integrated Multi-satellite Retrievals for GPM
ISV	Intraseasonal Variability
ITCZ	The Intertropical Convergence Zone
JHPCN	The Joint Usage/Research Center for Interdisciplinary Large-scale Information Infrastructures
MAM	March–April–May
MSC	Meso-scale Convective System
MIO	Madden-Julian Oscillation
nextGEMS	Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems
NICAM	Nonhydrostatic Icosahedral Atmospheric Model
ORCESTRA	Organized Convection and EarthCARE Studies over the Tropical Atlantic
OSTIA	The Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Ice Analysis
PCMDI	Program for Climate Model Diagnosis & Intercomparison
PDC	Precipitation Diurnal Cycle
SCREAM	The Simple Cloud-Resolving E3SM Atmosphere Model
SON	September–October–November
SPCZ	The South Pacific Convergence Zone
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
STAs	Storm Track Activities
SYPD	Simulated Years Per Day
TRMM	Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission
UM	Unified Model

Acknowledgements

We thank various discussions throughout a series of international conferences held in 2022–2024: CFMIP2022 (Seattle, USA), PAN-GASS2022 (Monterey, USA), ICCP-GSRA Workshop 2023 jointly with The 2nd EarthCARE Modeling Workshop (Shuzenji, Japan), Yamanaka ICCP-GSRA mini-workshop 2023 (Yamanakako, Japan), EVE in 2023 (Berlin, Germany), CFMIP2023 (Paris, France), The 6th international workshop on nonhydrostatic model (NHM WS 2023; Sapporo, Japan), AGU2023 (San Francisco, USA), The New York Meeting on Tropical Cyclones and Global Storm-Resolving Analysis in 2024 (New York, USA), and EGU2024 (Vienna, Austria). We thank Hans Segura and Andrew Gettelman for their comments on the manuscript before submission.

Author contributions

DT leads this intercomparison, conducts the NICAM simulation and analysis, writes the manuscript in cooperation with MS, and revises it. MS coordinates this project and leads the writing of the manuscript. BS and DK support the intercomparison and help archive data at DKRZ. TM, CK, PL, and CT contribute to the input of the manuscript.

Funding

This project is supported by JSPS Core-to-Core Program, “International Core-to-Core Project on Global Storm Resolving Analysis” (Grant Number: JPJSCCA20220001) and JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number 20B202, 20H05728, and 24K00703. The use of the mdx platform is supported by the “Joint Usage/Research Center for Interdisciplinary Large-scale Information Infrastructures

(JHPCN)” in Japan (Project ID: jh241009). This research used computational resources of the supercomputer Fugaku (ID:hp220058, hp220132, hp230078, hp230278, hp240106). This project is supported by DKRZ and WarmWorld from the Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (grant no. 01LK2202B) and EC Horizon 2020 (NextGEMS, grant no. 101003470). CT’s contribution was supported under the Energy Exascale Earth System Model (E3SM) project, funded by the U.S. Department of Energy and prepared under the auspices of the U.S. Department of Energy by Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory under Contract DE-AC52-07NA27344.

Availability of data and materials

The University of Tokyo and DKRZ will archive the intercomparison data for the proposed experiment. The mdx platform of JHPCN will be provided by the team of The University of Tokyo. The source code of NICAM is available on request, as described at <https://nicam.jp/>.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Received: 22 May 2024 Accepted: 15 November 2024

Published online: 19 December 2024

References

- Adam O, Schneider T, Briert F, Bischoff T (2016) Relation of the double-ITCZ bias to the atmospheric energy budget in climate models. *Geophys Res Lett* 43(14):7670–7677
- Bischoff T, Schneider T (2016) The equatorial energy balance, ITCZ position, and double-ITCZ bifurcations. *J Clim* 29(8):2997–3013
- Blackburn M, Hoskins BJ (2013) Context and aims of the aqua-planet experiment. *J Meteorol Soc Japan* 91A:1–15. <https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2013-A01>
- Bolot M, Harris LM, Cheng KY et al (2023) Kilometer-scale global warming simulations and active sensors reveal changes in tropical deep convection. *Npj Clim Atmos Sci* 6:209. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-023-00525-w>
- Cess RD, Potter GL, Blanchet JP, Boer GJ, Del Genio AD, Deque M et al (1990) Intercomparison and interpretation of climate feedback processes in 19 atmospheric general circulation models. *J Geophys Res* 95:16601–16615. <https://doi.org/10.1029/jd095id10p16601>
- Cheng K-Y, Harris L, Bretherton C, Merlis TM, Bolot M, Zhou L et al (2022) Impact of warmer sea surface temperature on the global pattern of intense convection: insights from a global storm resolving model. *Geophys Res Lett* 49:e2022GL099796. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL099796>
- Feng Z, Leung LR, Hardin J, Terai CR, Song F, Caldwell P (2023) Mesoscale convective systems in DYAMOND global convection-permitting simulations. *Geophys Res Lett* 50(4):e2022GL102603
- Haarsma RJ, Roberts MJ, Vidale PL, Catherine A, Bellucci A, Bao Q et al (2016) High resolution model intercomparison project (HighResMIP v1.0) for CMIP6. *Geosci Model Dev* 9:4185–4208. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-4185-2016>
- Hendon HH, Liebmann B (1990) A composite study of onset of the Australian summer monsoon. *J Atmos Sci* 47(18):2227–2240
- Hoffmann J, Bauer P, Sandu I, Wedi N, Geenen T, Thiemert D (2023) Destination earth—a digital twin in support of climate services. *Climate Services* 30:100394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2023.100394>

- Hohenegger C, Stevens B (2022) Tropical continents rainier than expected from geometrical constraints. *AGU Adv* 3:e2021AV000636. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021AV000636>
- Hohenegger C, Korn P, Linardakis L, Redler R, Schnur R, Adamidis P et al (2023) ICON-Sapphire: simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales. *Geosci Model Dev* 16:779–811. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-779-2023>
- Hoskins BJ, Yang G-Y (2021) The detailed dynamics of the Hadley cell Part II: december-February. *J Clim* 34:805–823
- Hoskins BJ, Yang G-Y, Fonseca RM (2020) The detailed dynamics of the June–August Hadley cell. *Quart J Roy Meteor Soc* 146:557–575
- Hou AY, Kakar RK, Neeck S, Azarbarzin AA, Kummerow CD, Kojima M et al (2014) The global precipitation measurement mission. *Bull Amer Meteor Soc* 95(5):701–722. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-13-00164.1>
- Hwang YT, Frierson DM (2013) Link between the double-intertropical convergence zone problem and cloud biases over the Southern Ocean. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 110(13):4935–4940
- Illingworth AJ, Barker HW, Beljaars A, Ceccaldi M, Chepfer H, Clerbaux N et al (2015) The earthcare satellite: the next step forward in global measurements of clouds, aerosols, precipitation, and radiation. *Bull Am Meteorol Soc* 96:1311–1332. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-12-00227.1>
- Judt F, Klocke D, Rios-Berrios R, Vanniere B, Ziemann B, Auger L, Biercamp J, Bretherton C, Chen X, Dueben P, Hohenegger C, Khairoutdinov M, Kodama C, Kornblueh C, Lin S-J, Nakano M, Neumann P, Putman W, Roeber W, Roberts M, Satoh M, Shibuya R, Stevens B, Vidale PL, Wedi N, Zhou L (2021) Tropical cyclones in global storm-resolving models. *J Meteor Soc Japan* 99:579–602. <https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2021-029>
- Kajikawa Y, Wang B, Yang J (2010) A multi-time scale Australian monsoon index. *Int J Climatol*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.1955>
- Kang SM, Frierson DM, Held IM (2009) The tropical response to extratropical thermal forcing in an idealized GCM: the importance of radiative feedbacks and convective parameterization. *J Atmos Sci* 66(9):2812–2827
- Kawatani Y, Takahashi M, Tokioka T (2004) Gravity waves around the subtropical jet of the southern winter in an atmospheric general circulation model. *Geophys Res Lett* 31(22):2004GL020794
- Kikuchi K (2021) The Boreal summer intraseasonal oscillation (BSISO): a review. *J Meteor Soc Japan* 99:933–972. <https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2021-045>
- Kinter JL III, Cash B, Achuthavariar D, Adams J, Altschuler E, Dirmeyer P, Doty B, Huang B, Marx L, Manganello J, Stan C, Wakefield T, Jin E, Palmer T, Hamrud M, Jung T, Miller M, Towers P, Wedi N, Satoh M, Tomita H, Kodama C, Nasuno T, Oouchi K, Yamada Y, Taniguchi H, Andrews P, Baer T, Ezell M, Halloy C, John D, Loftis B, Mohr R, Wong K (2013) Revolutionizing climate modelling—project athena: a multi-institutional, international collaboration. *Bull Amer Meteorol Soc* 94:231–245
- Kobayashi S, Ota Y, Harada Y, Ebata A, Moriya M, Onoda H, Takahashi K (2015) The JRA-55 reanalysis: general specifications and basic characteristics. *J Meteor Soc Japan* 93(1):5–48
- Kodama C, Ohno T, Seiki T, Yashiro H, Noda AT, Nakano M et al (2021) The nonhydrostatic icosahedral atmospheric model for CMIP6 HighResMIP simulations (NICAM16-S): experimental design, model description, and impacts of model updates. *Geosci Model Dev* 14:795–820. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-14-795-2021>
- Lee J, Hohenegger C (2024) Weaker land–atmosphere coupling in global storm-resolving simulation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 121(12):e2314265121
- Ma H-Y, Klein SA, Lee J, Ahn M-S, Tao C, Gleckler PJ (2022) Superior daily and sub-daily precipitation statistics for intense and long-lived storms in global storm-resolving models. *Geophys Res Lett* 49:e2021GL096759. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL096759>
- Matsui T, Tao WK, Munchak SJ, Grecu M, Huffman GJ (2015) Satellite view of quasi-equilibrium states in tropical convection and precipitation microphysics. *Geophys Res Lett* 42:1959–1968. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GL063261>
- Miura H (2019) Difficulties in the subgrid-scale redistribution of moisture of a global cloud-resolving model. *Curr Trends Represent Phys Process Weather Clim Model* 2019:207–217
- Miura H, Satoh M, Tomita H, Noda AT, Nasuno T, Iga SI (2007) A short-duration global cloud-resolving simulation with a realistic land and sea distribution. *Geophys Res Lett* 34(2):2006GL027448
- Miura H, Suematsu T, Kawai Y, Yamagami Y, Takasuka D, Takano Y, Hung C-S, Yamazaki K, Kodama C, Kajikawa Y, Masumoto Y (2023) Asymptotic matching between weather and climate models. *Bull Am Meteorol Soc* 104:E2308–E2315. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-22-0128.1>
- Miyakawa T, Takayabu YN, Nasuno T, Miura H, Satoh M, Moncrieff MW (2012) Convective momentum transport by rainbands within a Madden–Julian oscillation in a global nonhydrostatic model with explicit deep convective processes. Part I: methodology and general results. *J Atmos Sci* 69(4):1317–1338
- Miyakawa T, Yashiro H, Suzuki T, Tatebe H, Satoh M (2017) A madden-Julian oscillation event remotely accelerates ocean upwelling to abruptly terminate the 1997/1998 super El Niño. *Geophys Res Lett* 44:9489–9495. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL074683>
- Moncrieff MW, Liu C, Bogenschutz P (2017) Simulation, modeling, and dynamically based parameterization of organized tropical convection for global climate models. *J Atmos Sci* 74(5):1363–1380
- Müller OV, Vidale PL, Vannière B, Schiemann R, Senan R, Haarsma RJ, Jungclaus JH (2021) Land-atmosphere coupling sensitivity to GCMs resolution: a multimodel assessment of local and remote processes in the sahel hot spot. *J Clim* 34:967–985. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-20-0303.1>
- Nakano M, Yashiro H, Kodama C, Tomita H (2018) Single precision in the dynamical core of a nonhydrostatic global atmospheric model: evaluation using a baroclinic wave test case. *Mon Wea Rev* 146(2):409–416
- Neale RB, Hoskins BJ (2000) A standard test for AGCMs and their physical parameterizations. I: the proposal. *Atmos Sci Letter* 1:101–107
- Oueslati B, Bellon G (2015) The double ITCZ bias in CMIP5 models: Interaction between SST, large-scale circulation and precipitation. *Clim Dyn* 44:585–607
- Peixoto JP, Oort AH (1984) Physics of climate. *Rev Mod Phys* 56(3):365
- Plougonven R, Teitelbaum H, Zeitlin V (2003) Inertia gravity wave generation by the tropospheric midlatitude jet as given by the fronts and atlantic storm-track experiment radio soundings. *J Geophys Res Atmos* 108(D21):2003JD003535
- Priestley MD, Ackerley D, Catto JL, Hodges KI, McDonald RE, Lee RW (2020) An overview of the extratropical storm tracks in CMIP6 historical simulations. *J Clim* 33(15):6315–6343
- Rackow T, Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia X, Becker T, Milinski S, Sandu I, Aguridan R, Ziemann F (2024) Multi-year simulations at kilometre scale with the integrated forecasting system coupled to FESOM2. 5/NEMOV3. 4. EGU sphere, 2024, pp 1–59
- Reed KA, Stansfield AM, Wehner MF, Zarzycki CM (2020) Forecasted attribution of the human influence on Hurricane Florence. *Sci Adv* 6(1):eaaw9253
- Reed KA, Wehner MF, Zarzycki CM (2022) Attribution of 2020 hurricane season extreme rainfall to human-induced climate change. *Nat Comm* 13(1):1905
- Roh W, Satoh M (2014) Evaluation of precipitating hydrometeor parameterizations in a single-moment bulk microphysics scheme for deep convective systems over the tropical central Pacific. *J Atmos Sci* 71(7):2654–2673
- Roh W, Satoh M, Hohenegger C (2021) Intercomparison of cloud properties in DYAMOND simulations over the Atlantic Ocean. *J Meteor Soc Japan* 99:1439–1451. <https://doi.org/10.2151/JMSJ.2021-070>
- Satoh M (2002) Conservative scheme for the compressible nonhydrostatic models with the horizontally explicit and vertically implicit time integration scheme. *Mon Wea Rev* 130(5):1227–1245. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(2002\)130%3c1227:CSFTCN%3e2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(2002)130%3c1227:CSFTCN%3e2.0.CO;2)
- Satoh M, Matsuno T, Tomita H, Miura H, Nasuno T, Iga S (2008) Nonhydrostatic icosahedral atmospheric model (NICAM) for global cloud resolving simulations. *J Comput Phys* 227:3486–3514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2007.02.006>
- Satoh M, Tomita H, Yashiro H, Miura H, Kodama C, Seiki T, Noda AT, Yamada Y, Goto D, Sawada M, Miyoshi T, Niwa Y, Hara M, Ohno Y, Iga S, Arakawa T, Inoue T, Kubokawa H (2014) The Non-hydrostatic icosahedral atmospheric model: description and development. *Prog Earth Planet Sci* 1:18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40645-014-0018-1>
- Satoh M, Stevens B, Judt F, Khairoutdinov M, Lin S, Putman WM, Düben P (2019) Global cloud-resolving models. *Curr Climate Change Rep* 5:172–184. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40641-019-00131-0>
- Schemm S (2023) Toward eliminating the decades-old “too zonal and too equatorward” storm-track bias in climate models. *J Adv Model Earth Syst* 15(2):e2022MS003482
- Segura H, Hohenegger C, Wengel C, Stevens B (2022) Learning by doing: seasonal and diurnal features of tropical precipitation in a global-coupled

- storm-resolving model. *Geophys Res Lett* 49:1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL101796>
- Sobel AH, Lee CY, Bowen SG, Camargo SJ, Cane MA, Clement A et al (2023) Near-Term tropical cyclone risk and coupled Earth system model biases. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 120:1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2209631120>
- Stephens G, Winker D, Pelon J, Trepte C, Vane D, Yuhas C et al (2018) CloudSat and CALIPSO within the A-train: ten years of actively observing the earth system. *Bull Am Meteorol Soc* 99:569–581. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-16-0324.1>
- Stevens B, Bony S (2013) What are climate models missing? *Science* 340:1053–1054. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1237554>
- Stevens B, Satoh M, Auger L, Biercamp J, Bretherton C, Düben P et al (2019) DYAMOND: the dynamics of the atmospheric general circulation modeled on non-hydrostatic domains. *Prog Earth Planet Sci* 6:1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40645-019-0304-z>
- Stevens B, Adami S, Ali T, Anzt H, Aslan Z, Attinger S, Bäck J, Baehr J, Bauer P, Bernier N, Bishop B, Bockelmann H, Bony S, Bouchet V, Brasseur G, Bresch DN, Breyer S, Brunet G, Buttigieg PL, Cao J, Castet C, Cheng Y, Choudhury AD, Coen D, Crewell S, Dabholkar A, Dai Q, Doblus-Reyes F, Durran D, El Gaidi A, Ewen C, Exarchou E, Eyring V, Falkinoff F, Farrell D, Forster PM, Frassoni A, Frauen C, Fuhrer O, Gani S, Gerber E, Goldfarb D, Grieger J, Gruber N, Hazeleger W, Herken R, Hewitt C, Hoefler T, Hsu H-H, Jacob D, Jahn A, Jakob C, Jung T, Kadow C, Kang I-S, Kang S, Kashinath K, Königslöw K-V, Klocke D, Kloenne U, Klöwer M, Kodama C, Kollet S, Kölling T, Kontkanen J, Kopp S, Koran M, Kulmala M, Lappalainen H, Latifi F, Lawrence B, Lee JY, Lejeun Q, Lessig C, Li C, Lippert T, Luterbacher J, Manninen P, Marotzke J, Matsouoka S, Merchant C, Messmer P, Michel G, Michielsen K, Miyakawa T, Müller J, Munir R, Narayanasetti S, Ndiaye O, Nobre C, Oberg A, Oki R, Özkan-Haller T, Palmer T, Posey S, Prein A, Primus O, Pritchard M, Pullen J, Putrasahan D, Quaas J, Raghavan K, Ramaswamy V, Rapp M, Rauser F, Reichstein M, Revi A, Saluja S, Satoh M, Schemann V, Schemm S, Poberaj CS, Schulthess T, Senior C, Shukla J, Singh M, Slingo J, Sobel A, Solman S, Spitzer J, Stammer D, Stier P, Stocker T, Stroock S, Hang Su, Taalas P, Taylor J, Tegmeier S, Teutsch G, Tompkins A, Ulbrich U, Vidale P-L, Chien-Ming Wu, Hao Xu, Zaki N, Zanna L, Zhou T, Ziemann F (2024) Earth virtualization engines (EVE). *Earth Syst Sci Data* 16:2113–2122. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-16-2113-2024>
- Suematsu T, Miura H, Kodama C, Takasuka D (2022) Deceleration of Madden-Julian oscillation speed in NICAM AMIP-type simulation associated with biases in the Walker circulation strength. *Geophys Res Lett* 49(11):e2022GL098628
- Suematsu T, Peinado A, Takasuka D, Hung C-S, Kajikawa Y, Klocke D, Miura H, Tomita H (2023) Preliminary results from Im (DYAMOND3) an aquaplanet cloud-resolving model intercomparison project. The 2023 Joint CFMIP-GASS Meeting On Cloud, Precipitation, Circulation and Climate Sensitivity
- Sun Q, Miao C, Duan Q, Ashouri H, Sorooshian S, Hsu KL (2018) A review of global precipitation data sets: data sources, estimation, and intercomparisons. *Rev Geophys* 56(1):79–107
- Takasuka D, Kodama C, Suematsu T, Ohno T, Yamada Y, Seiki T, Masunaga R (2024) How can we improve the seamless representation of climatological statistics and weather toward reliable global K-scale climate simulations? *J Adv Model Earth Syst.* 16(2):2023003701
- Takasuka D, Kodama C, Suematsu T, Ohno T, Yamada Y, Takano Y, et al. (2023) Tackling errors toward realistic seamless representation in kilometer-scale climate simulations with NICAM. In: The 28th IUGG general assembly abstracts (Vol. 2023, pp IUGG23–3863
- Tanaka T, Kawase H, Imada Y, Kawai Y, Watanabe S (2023) Risk-based versus storyline approaches for global warming impact assessment on basin-averaged extreme rainfall: a case study for Typhoon Hagibis in eastern Japan. *Env Res Lett* 18(5):054010
- Taylor KE, Stouffer RJ, Meehl GA (2012) An overview of CMIP5 and the experiment design. *Bull Am Meteorol Soc* 93:485–498. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-11-00094.1>
- Taylor M, Caldwell PM, Bertagna L, Clevenger C, Donahue A, Foucar J, Guba O, Hillman B, Keen N, Krishna J, Norman M, Sreepathi S, Terai C, White JB, Salinger AG, McCoy RB, Ruby Leung L, Bader DC and Wu D (2023) The simple cloud-resolving E3SM atmosphere model running on the frontier exascale system. In: Proceedings of the international conference for high performance computing, networking, storage and analysis (SC'23). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 7, pp 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3581784.3627044>
- Tomita H (2008) New microphysical schemes with five and six categories by diagnostic generation of cloud ice. *J Meteorol Soc Japan* 86:121–142
- Tomita H, Satoh M (2004) A new dynamical framework of nonhydrostatic global model using the icosahedral grid. *Fluid Dyn Res* 34:357–400
- Wang B, Fan Z (1999) Choice of South Asian summer monsoon indices. *Bull Amer Meteor Soc* 80:629–638
- Wang B, Wu R, Lau K-M (2001) Interannual variability of Asian summer monsoon: contrast between the Indian and western North Pacific-East Asian monsoons. *J Clim* 14:4073–4090
- Webster PJ, Yang S (1992) Monsoon and ENSO: selectively interactive systems. *Quart J Roy Meteor Soc* 118:877–926
- World Climate Research Programme (2022) Report of the WCRP km-scale modeling workshop, 8/2022, 3–7 October 2022, hybrid format [Available at https://www.wcrp-climate.org/WCRP-publications/2022/WCRP_Report_08-2022_k-scale-report-final.pdf].
- Yokoi S, Kajikawa Y (2024) Precipitation diurnal cycle over tropical coastal regions represented in climate experiments with a global cloud-system resolving model. *SOLA* 20:145–151
- Zhao M, Knutson T (2024) Crucial role of sea surface temperature warming patterns in near-term high-impact weather and climate projection. *Npj Clim Atmos Sci* 7:130. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-024-00681-7>
- Zhou W, Xie SP (2017) Intermodel spread of the double-ITCZ bias in coupled GCMs tied to land surface temperature in AMIP GCMs. *Geophys Res Lett* 44(15):7975–7984

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